

International Journal of Network Security & Its Applications (IJNSA)

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Scope & Topics

The International Journal of Network Security & Its Applications (IJNSA) is a bi monthly open access peer-reviewed journal that publishes articles which contribute new results in all areas of the computer Network Security & its applications. The journal focuses on all technical and practical aspects of security and its applications for wired and wireless networks. The goal of this journal is to bring together researchers and practitioners from academia and industry to focus on understanding Modern security threats and countermeasures, and establishing new collaborations in these areas.

Topics of Interest include, but are not limited to, the following:

- Network and Wireless Network Security
- Mobile, Ad Hoc and Sensor Network Security
- Peer-to-Peer Network Security
- Database and System Security
- Intrusion Detection and Prevention
- Internet Security & Applications
- Security & Network Management
- E-mail security, Spam, Phishing, E-mail fraud
- Virus, worms, Trojan Protection
- Security threats & countermeasures (DDoS, MiM, Session Hijacking, Replay attack etc.)
- Ubiquitous Computing Security
- Web 2.0 security
- Cryptographic protocols
- Performance Evaluations of Protocols & Security Application

Paper submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through e-mail ijnsa@airccse.org Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal.

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline** : May 26, 2018
- Notification : June 26, 2018
- Final Manuscript Due : July 08, 2018
- Publication Date: Determined by the Editor-in-Chief

For other details please visit <http://airccse.org/journal/ijnsa.html>